

DYNAMIC COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH AND FAILURE OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINIUM METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: Dynamic compressive behaviour of 5~15 V_f % carbon fiber reinforced 7075 Al metal matrix composite has been studied at room temperature at strain rates from about 10^{-1} s^{-1} to $3.5 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The low rate tests were performed using a Saginomiya 100 metal forming machine, while a compressive split Hopkinson bar was used for high strain rate tests. In addition to the determination of dynamic properties, the influence of strain rate and fiber volume fraction on the microstructure and fracture mechanisms were investigated using optical and scanning electron microscopy. The resulting data indicate that impact response of the tested composite is affected both by applied strain rate and fiber volume fraction, resulting in variations of work hardening rate, strain rate sensitivity and activation volume. The deformed microstructure at both low and high strain rates displayed extensive unstable plastic flow of Al matrix associated with catastrophic fiber fragmentation. Fiber breakage is dominated mostly by shearing and tension, and a relatively shorter fiber fragment length is found at high rate conditions. Fracture behaviour and the damage process of the tested composite depend quite strongly on the strain rate.

KEYWORDS: Aluminum metal matrix composite, carbon fiber, split compressive Hopkinson bar, impact strength, strain rate effect, unstable plastic flow, dynamic failure, microstructural evolution.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing utilization of metal matrix composites (MMCs) within structural applications has been driven largely by the high specific stiffness and specific strength exhibited by these materials. These properties, together with good oxidation and corrosion resistance, make MMCs strong candidates for use with aerospace applications. In many of these applications, dynamic impact loading may occur, for example, in the sudden impact of foreign objects on aircraft turbine blades or during automobile collisions. The basic features of material failure under static loading may be entirely different than those under dynamic loading for MMC materials. Therefore, the impact dynamic response and fracture characteristics of MMC are very important for present and future applications in these industries. It is generally accepted that the 7075 Al alloy develops the highest strength among the Al alloys, and it is commonly used to make certain aircraft components. By embedding or dispersing high strength and high modulus carbon fiber within the alloy, there is the possibility of achieving even higher specific

properties. The performance and mechanical response of a metal matrix composite are highly dependent on the type of loading, and particularly on the reinforcement's interfacial bonding and geometrical properties, this latter including size, shape and orientations of the reinforcements[1-4].

From the plastic deformation viewpoint, the flow resistance of Al metal matrix composite is affected strongly by the loading rate associated with different deformation mechanisms. Increased utilization of 7075 Al metal matrix composite under various loading conditions requires an understanding of the relationship between mechanical response as a function of microstructure in order to guide future composite design and to develop constitutive models to predict composite behaviour. Numerous experimental studies have probed the quasi-static mechanical behaviour of 7075 Al metal matrix composite under tensile loading, and most of these have been conducted on particulate and whisker reinforced composite [5-7]. However, studies conducted on the impact response over a wide strain rate range are scanty, especially for a laminated carbon fiber reinforced 7075 Al metal matrix composite. It seems desirable, then, to study the macroscopic response of this composite to large strains developed at high rates of deformation. The objective of this study is to characterize the dynamic impact response of carbon fiber reinforced Al metal matrix composite by means of a Hopkinson bar at strain rates ranging from 10^{-1} s^{-1} to 10^3 s^{-1} . The impact flow resistance and fracture behaviour are also described in terms of strain rate and fiber volume fraction. All dynamic results are compared with those of low rate testing performed at 10^{-1} s^{-1} .

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

High strength 7075 Al alloy, having a nominal composition (wt. %) of Al-5.6Zn-2.6Mg-1.6Cu, was chosen as the matrix material. Tairyfil C06K42 carbon fibers, provided by Formosa Plastic Corporation, Taiwan, of 10 μm average diameter, were obtained on a spool packed in tows of 2000 filaments. The composite material was fabricated by the conventional metal casting technique using a permanent metallic mold and was heat-treated to the T6 condition. Fiber volume fractions of 5%, 10% and 15% were used. Before casting, the carbon fibers were first woven into a two dimensional laminated net form lying $\pm 90^\circ$. The woven fiber was next deposited with a thin layer of copper by the CVD method in order to improve the bonding strength between the fiber and the Al matrix. Then the 7075 aluminum alloy was melted at 750°C using an electric furnace. After the carbon fiber was positioned and incorporated into the mold at the desired volume fraction, the molten aluminum was cast into the heated metallic mould at a temperature of 710°C . Additional hydraulic pressure of 100 MPa was applied to obtain melt infiltration during casting.

Cylindrical specimens of height 10mm and diameter 10mm were machined with an EDM device from the composite ingot, which had dimensions of $200 \times 150 \times 20 \text{ mm}$. During testing, the ends were lubricated with molybdenum disulfide grease to minimize friction effects. Fig. 1 shows schematically the geometry of composite test specimens. The prepared specimens were tested under uniaxial compression both statically and dynamically under varying loads and strain rates at room temperature. The loading direction was perpendicular to the carbon fiber layer for all the tests. Material characteristics at the low strain rate of 10^{-1} s^{-1} were measured using a Saginomiya 100 metal forming machine. Dynamic compression tests at strain rates of 1300 s^{-1} , 2300 s^{-1} and 3300 s^{-1} were conducted using a split Hopkinson pressure bar. This device utilizes measurements of elastic waves in hardened steel pressure bars to determine the relative motion of the two faces of the test specimens and the associated

stress. A full description of the utilized technique for obtaining dynamic property data is included in reference [8].

Microstructure was examined using optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Specimens for optical metallography were sectioned diametrically along their central axis from the deformed samples, then polished conventionally and etched using an acidic solution (10ml H₂O, 10ml HNO₃, 10ml HCl and 5ml HF). An MeF3 optical microscope was used for microstructural observations. Fracture specimens were examined using a JEOL JAX-840 scanning electron microscope operating at an accelerating potential of 20kV.

Fig.1: Schematic presentation of geometry of compression specimen of composite.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Flow Stress-strain Behaviour

Typical flow stress-strain curves of carbon fiber reinforced 7075 Al metal matrix composite deformed at various strain rates for carbon fiber volume fractions of 5% and 15% are shown in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b), respectively. The curves shown represent the average results of three samples tested at each strain rate. The results show that the flow stress-strain behaviour of the tested composite is fairly sensitive both to strain rate and fiber volume fraction. The dynamic strength exceeds its low rate strength by as much as 35%, and the difference in strength between the dynamic and low rate specimens increases with the fiber volume fraction. If we focus on the effect of strain rate and fiber volume fraction on the fracture elongation and yield strength, it is found that for a given strain rate, the yielding strength increases with the fiber volume fraction. Under a fixed fiber volume fraction, the dynamic yielding strength is nearly three times higher than that of low rate specimens. The highest fracture elongation appears at low rate loading conditions. However, in the dynamic region, an increase of fracture strain with increasing strain rate is observed. Furthermore, for the higher reinforcing material volume fractions under higher strain rates, large fracture strain is also apparent. Obviously, the carbon fiber provides an improvement of ductility and leads to an enhancement in flow stress.

The slope of the stress strain curves in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b) can be used to define the work hardening rate of the tested composite at a given fiber volume fraction and strain rate. Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) represent the variation of the work hardening rate of carbon fiber reinforced 7075 Al metal matrix composite as a function of strain, strain rate at fiber volume fractions of 5% and 15%, respectively. It is clear that for a given fiber volume fraction under a specific strain rate, the work hardening rate, $d\sigma / d\varepsilon$, decreases very rapidly for small strains and very slowly for large strains. Furthermore, over the whole strain range, the work hardening rate at

Fig. 2: Typical true stress-strain curves of carbon fiber reinforced 7075 Al metal matrix composite deformed at various strain rates, with fiber volume fractions of (a) 5% and (b) 15%.

the low strain rate of 0.1 s^{-1} is always greater than those at the dynamic strain rates. This is due to high homogenous plastic flow occurring in the early stages of deformation for low rate specimens. Although a high work hardening behavior is observed at low rate conditions, in the dynamic range, the work hardening rate measured at true strains under 0.1 increases slightly with strain rate. Because of high strain rates, a rapid generation of dislocation and an increase of the dislocation multiplication rate may enhance the work hardening of the tested composite. However if the true strain is over 0.1, the work hardening rate becomes insignificantly dependent on strain rate. This can be explained by the fact that during dynamic impact deformation, work hardening behaviour is dominated by a competition process between 1) strain rate hardening resulting from the production, motion and interference of dislocation and 2) thermal softening caused by an increase in specimen temperature as a result of deformation heat. With increasing strain rate and large deformation, thermal softening increases until it becomes stronger than the work hardening rate and dominates the deformation behaviour. It can be observed in Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) that the fiber volume fraction does not affect the work hardening rate at the tested conditions. This suggests that the work hardening rate of the tested composite is dominated primarily by the Al metal matrix.

Fig. 3: Variation of work hardening rate as a function of strain and strain rate under fiber volume fractions of (a) 5%, and (b) 15%.

The Effect of Strain Rate

The above flow stress-strain response shows that the plastic flow of the tested composite increases with increasing strain rate. This strain rate effect can be more clearly observed by plotting the flow stress as a function of the logarithm of the strain rate. Fig. 4 shows the relationship between the flow stress and strain rate at a fixed true strain of 0.15 for the three fiber volume fractions. In this figure, three low rate data plots are also shown for comparison. It is evident, on the basis of Fig. 4, that there are two distinct regions corresponding to different strain rate sensitivities. In the low strain rate range, the flow stress increases only gradually with strain rate and can be approximately represented by a linear function of the logarithm of the strain rate. However, when the strain rate rises above 10^3 s^{-1} , there is a sharp change in behaviour as evidenced by the sudden increase in flow stress with strain rate. The same behaviour of increased rate sensitivity has been observed for many metallic materials such as aluminum [9] and high strength alloy steels [10]. The strain rate value at which the functional dependence of σ on $\ln \dot{\epsilon}$ departs from linearity is of considerable interest, since a change in the functional dependence of stress on strain rate implies that a different deformation mechanism is dominating plastic flow behaviour. At strain rates lower than 10^3 s^{-1} , deformation is believed to be controlled by thermal activation, and the strength of the material increases slowly with strain rate. However, at rates above about 10^3 s^{-1} , the deformation mechanism changes and is interpreted to be a result of either the increasing importance of dislocation drag or an enhanced rate of dislocation generation. In this high rate region, a direct linear dependence of flow stress on strain rate is often found.

Fig. 4: Relationship between flow stress and strain rate at fixed true strain of 0.15 for three fiber volume fractions.

Estimation of Strain Rate Sensitivity and Thermal Activation Volume

In order to calculate the strain rate sensitivity from the test data, we can define a strain rate sensitivity parameter as follows:

$$\beta = \left\{ \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \ln(\dot{\epsilon}_2 / \dot{\epsilon}_1)} \right\} = \frac{\sigma_2 - \sigma_1}{\ln(\dot{\epsilon}_2 / \dot{\epsilon}_1)} \quad (1)$$

where the compressive stresses σ_2 and σ_1 are obtained in tests conducted at the constant strain rates $\dot{\epsilon}_2$ and $\dot{\epsilon}_1$ respectively, and are calculated at the same value of compressive plastic strain. According to equation (1) and the results in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b), the values of strain rate sensitivity of the tested composite with the three fiber volume fractions can be

determined and represented as a function of the work hardening stress $\sigma - \sigma_y$ and fiber volume fraction. Fig. 5(a) shows plots of strain rate sensitivity versus work hardening stress for specimens with different fiber volume fractions. Straight lines fitted to the data show that the strain rate sensitivity of the flow stress obeys a Cottrell-Stokes law when $\ln \dot{\epsilon}$ is plotted against $\sigma - \sigma_y$, i.e. $\ln \dot{\epsilon}$ is proportional to $\sigma - \sigma_y$. In addition, the slope of the line increases slightly with increasing fiber volume fraction. By comparing the changes of strain rate sensitivity caused by plastic deformation for different fiber volume fractions, one can notice that the increased strain rate sensitivity with fiber volume fraction is due to different work hardening rates and dislocation multiplication rates of the Al matrix, as well as the constraining effect of the carbon fiber reinforcement. On the other hand, the enhancement of work hardening stress at high strain rates is probably due to the fiber reinforcement's resistance to both plastic flow and dislocation motion, and the increase of compressive strength of the fibers at high strain rates.

Values of activation volume V^* are calculated using $V^* = KT / \dot{\epsilon}$, where K is Boltzmann's constant and T is the temperature in degrees absolute. Use of this equation presumes that the deformation mechanism is thermally activated and that the change in activation free energy ΔG necessary to overcome the barriers to flow is a linear function of applied stress. Fig. 5(b) shows plots of thermal activation volume, V^*/b^3 , as a function of work hardening stress, $\sigma - \sigma_y$. As can be seen from this figure, for a given fiber volume fraction, the activation volume decreases rapidly with the increase of work hardening stress. Also, the activation volumes at high work hardening stress are considerably smaller than those obtained at small work hardening stress. At small work hardening stress, the activation volumes are large for the specimen with a 15% fiber volume fraction, and they decrease with decreasing fiber volume fraction for a given value of $\sigma - \sigma_y$. A similar relationship between activation volume and work hardening stress has been observed in polycrystalline tungsten [11] and $Ni_3(Al, Hf) B$ single crystal [12].

Fig. 5: Strain rate sensitivity (a) and activation volume (b) as a function of work-hardening stress for tested composite with different fiber volume fractions.

Microstructural Observations

Microscopic observations show that the deformed microstructure of carbon fiber reinforced 7075 Al metal matrix composite depends not only upon loading conditions, but material

parameters as well. For impact loading, the strain rate appears to be the most dominant effect. As regards material parameters, a host of structural features of both the Al matrix and the reinforcing carbon fiber interact and control the response of the material. Via optical metallography, it was seen that both low and high rates generated extensive plastic flow of the Al matrix and associated fiber fragmentation, the latter being cumulative as strain and strain rate increased. In addition, increasing strain rate levels induced different types of damage.

Fig. 6(a) shows an optical micrograph of a 15 V_f % specimen deformed at a low rate of 10^{-1} s^{-1} . The fibers appeared extensively fractured by shearing as well as tension. Extensive matrix plastic flow around the fractured fibers is also evident. This is indicative of intense deformation occurring at 45° with respect to the compression axis. In compression, the planes of maximum shear stress are at 45° to the axis of compression, and the primary plastic deformation occurs on this plane. This intense plastic flow results in a catastrophic fragmentation of fibers by shear. Similar morphology of fiber fragmentation and matrix plastic flow were observed in samples tested at high strain rates, but the matrix deformation and fiber fracture were more pronounced. The appearance of such microstructure is shown in Fig. 6(b), which corresponds to a 15 V_f % specimen deformed at $2.3 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Again, plastic flow of the metal matrix causes carbon fibers first to move and then break along the plane of maximum shear stress. The plastic deformation of the matrix in the fracture region of fibers at high rates is much more superficial than that of lower rate conditions. Another interesting observation that can be made from study of the deformed microstructure is in regard to changes of fiber fragment length. At the low rate of 10^{-1} s^{-1} , Fig. 7(a), the average fiber fragment length is quite large, which points to the fact that lower transfer load is applied to the carbon fiber during the fracture process. In contrast, a short fiber length is observed in high strain rate specimens. Fig. 7(b) shows the microstructure of a 15 V_f specimen deformed at $2.3 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. In this high rate deformation, fibers are seen to be very heavily fragmented, demonstrating both the effectiveness of load transfer and the homogeneity of deformation in these dynamic tests. Detailed microstructural examination shows that microcracks and voids appear between fragments of the fractured fibers. The fracture path is observed to follow the process of nucleation, growth and coalescence of these microcracks and voids along the maximum shear direction. The density of microcracks and voids and the state of stress determine the final shape of the microfractures and the morphology of the resultant fracture surface.

Fig. 6: Optical micrographic aspects of 15 V_f % specimens deformed at strain rates of (a) 10^{-1} s^{-1} and (b) $2.3 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Fig. 7: Optical micrographs showing typical fiber size distribution: (a) 15 V_f % specimen deformed at 10^{-1} s^{-1} and (b) 15 V_f % specimen deformed at $2.3 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Fracture Feature Observations

SEM observations were made of some of the specimens tested at low and high strain rates. For a given strain rate, the general form of the fracture surface is found to be the same for all fiber volume fractions, but, under a fixed fiber volume fraction, the fracture features vary strongly with strain rate. Examination of a fracture surface obtained at a low rate of 10^{-1} s^{-1} , Fig. 8(a), reveals that the fracture is characterized by extensive fiber breakage, fiber pull-out and a large amount of decohesion at the fiber/matrix interface. The presence of interface decohesion indicates the weakness of the fiber/matrix interface. Furthermore, increased interface decohesion reduces effective load transfer to the fiber during deformation. This tends to support our microstructural observation and helps to explain why, at low rate loading, the fiber fragment length is generally long. On the other hand, the relatively smooth surface of the Al matrix shows that the fibers cleaved during the fracture process. Internal cracking is also seen in a few locations in the micrograph along the direction of fiber alignment.

When strain rates reach dynamic levels, i.e. around 10^3 s^{-1} , a distinct difference in fracture morphology is observed, as shown in Fig. 8(b). At this strain rate, the fracture surface shows much less debonding, and some pulled-out fiber can be seen in the fracture region. Comparing Fig. 8(a) with Fig. 8(b), it is seen that the composite exhibits a more ductile behaviour as a high strain rate is imposed. The constraining effect of the fiber and enhancement of the dislocation multiplication rate lead to a higher level of strength and ductility. Finally, at the highest tested strain rate of $3.3 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, Figs. 9(a) and 9(b), the fracture morphology is similar to that of the $2.3 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ tests. However, a comparison between Fig. 8(b) and Fig. 9(a) shows a greater density of strips of adhered Al matrix on fiber surfaces and an increased density of Al debris on the fracture surfaces as strain rate is increased. These debris are probably composed of Al tongues that were torn off during the test. At this highest strain rate, more fiber fractures with short fragment length are observed. The fracture also exhibits features that are consistent with fibers having moved considerable distances before final fracture.

Fig. 8: Fracture features of composite specimens deformed at (a) 10^{-1} s^{-1} and (b) $1.3 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Fig. 9: Fracture features of composites specimens deformed at strain rate of $3.3 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ showing: (a) strips of adhered Al matrix on fiber surface, and (b) matrix plastic flow around fibers.

CONCLUSIONS

The flow stress-strain behaviour of the tested composite is found to depend strongly on both strain rate and fiber volume fraction. An increase of strain rate or fiber volume fraction results in an increase of flow stress. The fracture strain also increases with strain rate and fiber volume fraction. In addition, the rate of work hardening is sensitive to the strain and strain rate, but relatively insensitive to fiber volume fraction. The strain rate dependence of stress indicates two regions of rate sensitivity. The increase of flow stress with strain rate is probably due to the rate sensitivity of the Al matrix, as well as the constraining effect of the carbon fiber reinforcement. Deformed microstructure exhibits extensive unstable plastic flow of Al matrix associated with catastrophic fiber fragmentation. The breakage of fiber is produced mostly by shearing and tension, and higher strain rates induce a relatively smaller fiber fragment length in the composite as the higher stresses developed in matrix are shared with the fibers. More extensive debonding and pull-out of fibers from the Al matrix during the fracture process are observed in low strain rate specimens, and, conversely, high rate fracture surfaces show much less debonding and very much less fiber pull-out. A greater density of Al debris and fiber fracture is noted in the specimens tested at high strain rates.

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